

DETERMINATION OF THE PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF HIGHLY QUALIFIED ATHLETES ON THE EXAMPLE OF WRESTLERS AND VOLEBOLISTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8030147>

Abstract: in this article ‘determination of the physical development of highly qualified athletes in the example of wrestlers and volebolers’, their height is determined when standing and sitting, weight and chest circumference are inhaled and exhaled, and the results obtained are calculated based on comparison.

Keywords: physical development, high-rise athletes, wrestling, and volebolists, weight, height length and chest circumference, development indicators.

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ СПОРТСМЕНОВ ВЫСОКОЙ КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ НА ПРИМЕРЕ БОРЦОВ И ВОЛЬБОЛИСТОВ

Аннотация: в данной статье «определение физического развития спортсменов высокой квалификации на примере борцов и вольболистов» определяется их рост в положении стоя и сидя, вес и окружность грудной клетки на вдохе и выдохе, а полученные результаты рассчитываются на основе сравнение.

Ключевые слова: физическое развитие, спортсмены-высотники, борцы и вольболисты, вес, рост, длина и окружность грудной клетки, показатели развития.

INTRODUCTION

Physical fitness of athletes is considered one of the important components of sports training, and physical qualities – a process aimed at the development of strength, endurance, flexibility, agility and agility.

The main physical training tasks of Greek rum wrestlers are as follows:

- increase the level of health of athletes and the functional capabilities of different systems of their organism;
- the development of physical qualities in a unit that meets the peculiarity of sports wrestling.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Physical development is divided into general, auxiliary and special training. To achieve high results in physical fitness, the foundation is the necessary basis. It mainly ensures the resolution of the following tasks:

- comprehensive harmonic development of the wrestler's body, increasing its functional capabilities, developing physical qualities;
- increase the level of Health;
- the correct use of active rest during periods of intense training and competition loads.

General physical fitness involves the accumulation of various tools. Among them, exercises performed on projectiles and with projectiles, exercises performed on a special track with a partner, general developmental exercises taken from other sports: acrobatics, athletics, sports games, swimming, etc. are distinguished.

It is designed to create a special basis necessary for the effective execution of a large-scale work aimed at the development of special movement skills of athletes. It has a much narrower and more specific direction and solves the following tasks:

-develop qualities that are mostly more typical for wrestling;
- selective development of muscle groups involved to a large extent in the actions of the wrestler.
Based on the above data, the size and norm of the load size are determined on the basis of the methodology for determining the effect and direction of downloads in the training process of the Greek rum wrestler (see table 3.2.1).

As advanced means of auxiliary physical training, such exercises are used that, due to their kinematic and dynamic composition and the nature of neuromuscular tension, are suitable for the main actions that wrestling-Chi performs in competition activities. Among such exercises, the following can be distinguished:

- exercises performed on special trainer devices;

Table 1. Determination of the physical development of highly qualified athletes on the example of wrestlers and volebolists

№	Indications of physical development	In wrestlers			In volleyball player			
		mathematical sign	X	σ	V	X	σ	V
1	Height (cm)	When standing	170	5,9	3,4	177	6,2	3,5
		When sitting	90.3	3,7	4,0	91.7	3,8	4,7
		Weight (kg)	73.9	2,9	3,9	68	2,8	4,1
3	Chest circumference (cm)	When inhaled	102	3,8	3,7	95	3,3	3,4
		When exhaling	95.6	3,5	3,6	90.4	3,1	3,4

The dynamics of indicators of physical development of highly qualified athletes were studied. We compared the indicators of physical development of wrestling and volebolists. In the studies carried out on this, 40 high-Malian volebolians and wrestlers were involved. When determining the physical development of wrestlers, their standing height was measured (CM) the results were akd as follows. The wrestlers ' height average when walking upright was $x \pm \sigma$, 170 ± 5.9 CM, and the V variation coficent was 3.4 percent, whereas in volebolchians the average was $x \pm \sigma$, 177 ± 6.2 cm, and the V variation coficent was 3.4 percent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The wrestlers ' height average when sitting was $X \pm \sigma$, 90.3 ± 3.7 cm, and the V variation coficent was 4.0 percent, whereas in volebolists the average was $X \pm \sigma$, 91.7 ± 3.8 cm, and the V variation coficent was 4.7 percent.

The average weight of wrestlers was $X \pm \sigma$, 73.9 ± 2.9 kg, while the V variation coficent was 3.9% in volebolists, the average was $x \pm \sigma$, 68 ± 2.8 kg, and the V variation coficent was 4.1%.

The wrestlers had an average of $X \pm \sigma$, 95.6 ± 3.5 cm when the chest circumference was inhaled, while the V variation coefficient was 3.6 percent in volebolchians, the average was $X \pm \sigma$, 90.4 ± 3.1 cm, and the V variation coefficient was 3.4 percent.

Wrestlers had an average of $X \pm \sigma$, 102 ± 3.8 cm when the chest circumference was exhaled, and a V variational coefficient of 3.7 percent, whereas in volebolists the average was $X \pm \sigma$, 95 ± 3.3 cm, and a V variational coefficient of 3.4 percent.

Special physical training of wrestlers is aimed at developing the qualities of movement in strict accordance with the requirements imposed by the features of the competition activities of wrestlers.

The special physical training of volebolists and wrestlers is mainly carried out on the wrestling carpet and focuses on the development of the most important qualities of movement in the structure of movement qualifications. Therefore, competition exercises are used, involving various possible complications as the main tools of special physical training. Such complex exercises enhance the effect on the wrestler's body. For example, throwing a partner in a heavier weight class, training and training contests are performed with the replacement of partners, etc.k. This is all the exercises that make it possible to develop one or another mechanism of energy supply, have an integrated effect on the training of the wrestler, and at the same time increase his physical and technical-tactical training.

Figure 1 indicators of struggle and physical development of volebolists

All indicated types of physical fitness are inextricably linked with each other. Failure to adequately assess any type of fitness during the training process will ultimately prevent increased athletic performance. Therefore, it is very important to adhere to the optimal ratio of the types of physical fitness indicated in the training process. Its numerical expression is not considered a constant size, but varies depending on the qualifications of the wrestlers, their individual characteristics, the period of the training process and the state of the organism at that time.

CONCLUSION

Highly qualified athletes were determined to develop physically, and the results of the competition in wrestlers and volebolists show that the volebolists are noticeably taller than the

wrestlers in height, and the chest circumference has developed significantly higher than that of the volebolists.

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